

A REVIEW ON NANOBUBBLES: A NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Ramesh Metta, D. Vinay Kumar, K. Srinivas Reddy

ABSTRACT:

The emerging branch in pharmaceutical sciences known as pharmaceutical nanotechnology presents new tools, opportunities and scope, which are expected to have significant applications, in disease diagnostics and therapeutics. There is a growing interest in Nanobubble (NB) technology because of its wide range of potential applications in theranostics and targeted drug delivery including anticancer drug delivery, gene delivery etc. Nanobubbles could offer several features in anticancer drug delivery, improving cellular uptake of chemotherapy drugs into cancer cell lines. Nanobubbles opened a new field of ultrasound imaging and were used as a diagnostic method. This review describes the introduction, classification, stability of nanobubble, method of preparation, applications and challenges and future prospects.

INTRODUCTION:

Nanobubbles are also known as ultrafine bubbles which extremely gas bubbles with the size range is less than $1\mu\text{m}$. The advances in pharmaceutical research results in the creation of nanobubbles which is used for the treatment and detection of diseases in clinical purposes [1]. Nanobubbles are round, globular with a shell and a gas-filled core structure that enables them to perceptibly dynamic properties. Nanobubbles are comprise with gas core and stabilizing shells [2]. The nanobubbles shell part mostly consists of lipid, protein, surfactant /cosurfactant, polymer and polyelectrolyte multilayer. The shell can affects the half-life of nanobubbles. The nanobubbles core part can be charge with different gases such as oxygen, sulfur hexaflouride and perfluorocarbons. (figure 1) [3]. A change in the chemical components of fluid viscosity, ultrasound contrast agents, acoustic pressure, ambient temperature and pressure, gas diffusivity and size distribution can affect echogenicity and stability of ultrasound constrast agent which affects the property of shell and threshold of nonlinear bubble activity.[4]

Figure 1: Diagrammatic Representation of Nanobubble structure

The nanobubbles are designed as the delivery of drug, gene and gas. The design of a nanobubbles drug delivery system include co-delivery, target drug delivery, direct drug delivery, stimuli responsive drug delivery. [5]. Nanobubbles might be provide with enhanced stability and longer residence time in systemic circulation. Nanobubbles size range about $<1\mu\text{m}$, may be expected to have some priority in ultrasound molecular imaging. The enhanced permeability and retention [EPR] effects, Nanobubbles can be transferred from blood vessels into tissues even cells to be potentially imaging by ultrasound after accumulation [2]. Johnson and Cooke (1981) was first reported BNBs in sea water when they presented the early evidence of gas-filled bubbles by showing that pressure changes caused the bubbles to grow or shrink. The team claimed that the stability of submicron bubbles is unexpected as “very small bubbles should dissolve rapidly in response due to their surface tension pressures”, which deviates from the classical theory by Epstein and Plesset (1950) [6].

CLASSIFICATION OF NANOBUBBLES:

Nanobubbles are differently based on their size and position at the interface which is illustrated. Nanobubbles are classified into two types surface nanobubbles and bulk nanobubbles.

- 1) **Surface Nanobubbles:** These are gas filled bubbles are formed on the solid surface of the liquid. The height of nanobubbles can be $>10\mu\text{m}$ and $<100\mu\text{m}$ and radius of contact is between 50 and 500nm.
- 2) **Bulk Nanobubbles:** These are gas filled spherical bubbles with diameter is $<1000\text{nm}$. The bulk nanobubbles are categorized into two forms (i) free nanobubbles are formed without a shell

in liquid phase and (ii) encapsulated nanobubbles that exist with a stable shell comprising polymers, phospholipids / proteins. [2,5]

Figure 2: a) Surface Nanobubbles and b) Bulk Nanobubbles

PREPARATION METHODS:

1. Sonication Method:

Sonication is the process of applying high intensity ultrasound to disperse a gas or liquid in a suspension of an appropriate coating material. Emulsifiers are gases or liquids that create a suspension of microbubbles with a coating of, say, protein or surfactant which is immediately adsorbed onto their surfaces. A combination of span 60 and PEG 40S was ultrasonically sonicated to create biocompatible nanobubbles, which were then separated by centrifugation to produce a population of nanosized bubbles with a unimodal size distribution. Briefly the DSPC:DSPE[4:1 mol ratio] were dissolved in the methanol:chloroform[1:2v/v]. After the solvents were thinly layered using a rotary evaporator, they were hydrated for 45 minutes at 60°C in phosphate buffer saline. To create nanobubbles, the suspension was sonicated for 30 seconds while gas purging was going on. [2,7]

2. Microfluidic Method:

The creation of nanobubbles by microfluidic devices has been studied recently because it allows for fine control over bubble diameter and production rate through the interplay of device size distributions, liquid flow rate, and gas pressures. To control the size and dispersion of the MNBs, variables such as flow rate, pressure, liquid solution viscosity, and device orifice size can be adjusted. The two primary techniques for creating microfluidic devices are as follows: 1) Flow focussing units are made using soft lithography techniques; 2) Capillaries are built mechanically from a polymeric block. In all scenarios, the liquid and gas flow into a T-jn. The size of the

orifice and other device characteristics determine the MNBs that are subsequently generated in the T-jn. [2,8]

3. Emulsification Method:

The process of emulsification is typically used to create polymer shell nanobubbles. Water is created in an oil emulsion with a carrier polymer in this process, and the emulsion is then further emulsified in a significant amount of water. To create a solid polymer shell, the solvent is evaporated, and core gas is then added to lyophilized shells. A wider spectrum of nanobubble sizes has been created by using a high shear emulsification technique. A limited size distribution of nanobubbles has been produced via a membrane emulsification technique. This is accomplished by using a porous membrane. Permeating the membrane, gas bubbles spread out into a continuous phase that flows over its surface. Coalescence is avoided by adding emulsifiers. [2,9]

4. Mechanical Agitation Method:

The process of mechanical agitation can enhance the contact between the gas phase and the liquid phase containing surfactants while creating nanobubbles. The liquid solution can be shaken at several thousand oscillations per minute to create nanobubbles, particularly those with lipid shells. Bubbles of varying sizes will result from this. A desired gas is perfused from the top of a container filled with the required coating material in the liquid phase, and the container is then mechanically agitated to allow the shell material to encapsulate the desired gas in nanobubbles. A promising technique for industrially producing micro nanobubbles is a mechanical agitation. [2,10]. Etchepare et al. conducted experiments regarding the preparation of

BNBs by using the mechanical stirring method, the experimental set up shown in Figure 3. [16]

Figure 3: Mechanical agitation method

5. Ink-Jet Technique:

An ink-jet technique has been used to create microbubbles, where a polymer is pushed through a piezo-driven ink-jet nozzle of the appropriate size based on the application. The bubbles that develop are extracted from the nozzle by the pulses that the piezoelectric crystals produce in the fluid. A similar technique has also been used to create ultrafine oxygen nanobubbles using a high-pressure flow through the nozzle from pure water and an oxygen supply. [2,11]

6. Laser Ablation Technique:

The laser ablation process, which produces tiny nanobubbles, is also referred to as a stochastic method. Particles of aluminium oxide in water can be targeted by a specific wavelength of an excimer laser to create oxidized nanoparticles. Additionally, bubbles will form at the solid-liquid contact throughout the operation. The nanoclusters of aluminium oxide stabilize the bubbles. [2,12]

NANOBUBBLES STABILITY:

The ability of nanobubbles to endure under particular circumstances is known as their stability. Their stability depends on a number of variables, such as the solution's characteristics, surface tension, and the bubbles' surface charge. The stability of nanobubbles is primarily due to their surface charge. Higher zeta potential nanobubbles are more stable. Nevertheless, nanobubbles' zeta potential diminishes with time. Research shows that the bubble size actually rises, despite the fact that gas diffusion predicts that it should decrease. This process is described to the combined effects of brownian motion and zeta potential reduction, which result in the formation of larger bubbles and bubble coalescence.[13]

APPLICATIONS:

1. Malaria Detection:

Hemozoin is a substance that is created when blood-sucking mosquitoes ingested the blood. "Malaria pigment" is another term of hemozoin. For bloodsucking mosquitoes to survive, hemozoin formation and presence are vital. Hemozoin is therefore considered a target for the

creation of novel and forthcoming medications for the treatment of malaria. A non-invasive technique for detecting malaria has been developed using nanobubbles. For a brief period of time, around one picosecond, hemozoin nanoparticles are exposed to “safe” levels of laser pulse radiation with a near-infrared wavelength. A hemozoin vapour bubble forms around the hemozoin nanoparticles as a result of this radiation exposure. These hemozoin nanoparticles coated in vapor produce sonic signals that, when they come into contact with the skin, can identify malarial infections with animals. This new technique for identifying malarial infection is incredibly quick, easy, cheap, and secure.[14]

2. Gene Delivery:

Gene delivery can be accomplished with nanobubbles in an efficient manner without the need for viruses. The ultrasonic treatment of nanobubbles causes them to resonate and oscillate at different frequencies. Gene delivery is one area where this resonance property of nanobubbles can be used. The gene of interest can be extravasated from blood arteries by nanobubbles because of their small size. By readily entering the surrounding tissue, extravasation enables the nanobubbles to transfer the gene they carry in a highly targeted and non-invasive way.[14]

3. Cancer Treatment:

Nanobubbles that are stimulated by exposure to laser pulse radiation are known as plasmonic nanobubbles. Consequently, the cell surface develops a thin coating of liquid that has been vaporized. The goal of gold nanobubbles is to deliver drugs within cancer cells. These nanobubbles contain imbedded chemotherapy medicines. These nanobubbles can be inserted inside the tumor using a laser when chemotherapy medications are needed for cancer treatment. These nanobubbles are absorbed when the tumor membranes open up. The standard dosage of the chemotherapy medications is then released inside the tumor. [10,14]

4. Ultrasound Molecular Imaging:

Nanobubbles would be very redundant for imaging applications due to their small size. Lipid nanobubbles, on the other hand, have been discovered to be passively implicated in the ultrasonic imaging of cancer tissue. The tissues of tumours are very porous. As a result, the nanobubbles can readily infiltrate the tissue and remain there for a considerable amount of time. Red fluorescence dyes can be used to stain the tumours, revealing the existence of lipid nanobubbles in the specific tissue location that is impacted. [14,15]

5. Oxygen Delivery:

A decrease in dissolved oxygen concentration below physiologically normal levels, or hypoxia, has been found to be a key factor in the development of a number of illnesses, including numerous forms of cancer. Interest in administering medicinal gases has been increasing. Since a lack of oxygen flow to the tissues is linked to a number of medical disorders, including diabetes, burns, bedsores, and wounds, a lot of study has focused on oxygen delivery. Additionally, the primary characteristic of malignant solid tumors is oxygen deficient, which is accompanied by acidosis. Additionally, focused oxygen administration may complement antibiotic treatment for anaerobic illnesses. [17,18,19]

DRUGS USED IN NANOBUZZLES DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM:

Table 1: Some examples drugs are applicable in nanobubble

Drug	Shell	Core	References
Paclitaxel	DSPC:DSPE	Sulphur hexafluoride	[6]
Methotrexate	Poly (lactic-co- glycolic acid) (PLGA)	Perfluorocarbon	[20]
Paclitaxel	PLGA	Perfluoropropane	[21]
Mitomycin-C	Sodium cellulose carboxymethylcellulose	Oxygen	[22]
Biotinylated rabbit-IgG	1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC)	Perfluoropropane	[23]
Herceptin	Phospholipid	Octafluoropropane	[24]
Apatinib	DSPC and DSPE- PEG2000	Perfluoropropane	[25,26]
Apomorphine	Hydrogenated soybean phosphatidylcholine (SPC, Phospholipon1 80H)	Perfluoropentane	[27]
PDNA (pCMV - luciferase)	Distearoylphosphatidylcholine (DSPC)	Perfluoropropane	[28]

Camptothecin	DSPE-PEG2000	Perfluorobutane	[29]
Gene delivery	Chitosan	Perfluoropentane	[30]

CHALLENGES & FUTURE PROSPECTS OF NANOBUBBLES:

The factors should be considered in the formation of nanobubbles (a) the simple preparation method and reproducible with high yields, (b) the drug encapsulation percentage should be high, (c) the controllable pharmacokinetics, (d) possess favourable acoustic properties for ultrasound imaging.

Drug delivery system researched based on nanobubbles is still at the preliminary stage and the problem are focused on (a) when the US signal strength is weak, the nanobubbles sizes are decreases and the backscattering ability also weakened, which is an main problem to be solved in nanobubbles. The focus of future research will be to determine the how to improve their contrast enhancement capability by adjusting the contrast conditions of the bubble and optimizing the machine parameters. (b) the preparation process is difficult or time consuming. The stability of the NBs and the duration of circulation in vivo will be impacted, the complex preparation will be more expensive and more prone to contamination. (c) the low drug loading rate, improve the efficiency of drug loading and therapeutic effect with fewer doses of drugs is one of the goal on research. [5]

CONCLUSION:

Nanobubbles are the potential nanovehicle for the application in cancer treatment. Nanobubbles have various preparation method such as sonication method, microfluidic method, emulsification method, mechanical agitation method, ink-jet technique, laser agitation method. Nanobubbles are applicable for the gene delivery, oxygen delivery, ultrasound molecular imaging. The stability of nanobubbles based on the surfactant & polymers composition and size.

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